

A FRUITING ORANGE THORN

Thorns Are Modified Leaves or Branches. On Orange Trees They Are Nuisances.
Thornless Variety May Be Produced

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THE Century Dictionary defines a thorn as "a sharp excrescence on a plant: usually a branch or the termination of a stem or branch, indurated, leafless, and attenuated to a point." Botanically speaking, thorns are modified leaves or branches.

A striking illustration of the relationship of some thorns to branches is shown in the accompanying figures. These show the development of abnormally large thorns on rapidly growing branches of the Washington Navel Orange (*Citrus sinensis* (L.) Osbeck). Some of the thorns have developed into branches bearing fruit, leaves and secondary thorns. These varying stages of development illustrate the fact that, in the citrus, thorns are truly modified branches. (Figs. 8 and 9.)

THORN BEARS AN ORANGE

As can be seen in the illustration, one of the thorns bears a small orange. The young navel orange is borne at the tip of the thorn which also bears several small leaves and behaves like a fruiting branch of a navel orange tree.

Thorns in citrus trees, in cultivated orchards, are nuisances. They interfere with the work of picking the fruit, in that they are likely to injure the unprotected hands and arms of the

pickers. Instances are known where citrus pickers have suffered serious injuries from thorns, resulting in the loss of fingers, hands and eyes. Furthermore, the thorns are undesirable, as they frequently puncture the nearby fruits. These punctures offer opportunities for the entrance of various fungus diseases which often result in decay and loss of fruit. This decay may take place on the tree, but more frequently occurs after the fruits have been packed for the market. For these and other reasons citrus propagators and breeders have endeavored to propagate thornless strains.

It is a well-known fact that the size and number of thorns vary on the different trees of a variety and often on the different branches of the same tree. Through the selection of buds for propagation from thornless limbs, or those having small thorns, considerable progress has been made in isolating thornless strains, or strains in which the trees produce few and no thorns.

The variation of thorns in the citrus varieties, and in the strains of the same variety, is convincing evidence as to the heredity of this tree characteristic. The variation in thorniness on the trees of the same strain furnishes a basis for the isolation of thornless strains through systematic bud selection.

AN ORANGE THORN THAT BORE AN ORANGE

This orange thorn bears a young navel orange as well as several small leaves. It illustrates the fact that thorns may be merely modified branches. (Fig. 8.)

AN ORANGE THORN WHICH IS A NUISANCE

Instances are known where citrus pickers have suffered serious injuries from thorns, resulting in the loss of fingers, hands and eyes. Furthermore, thorns frequently puncture fruits and favor decay. Thornless varieties are desiderata. (Fig. 9.)

TYPICAL LEMON TREE FROM SELECTED BUD

A typical Lisbon lemon tree about 10 years old in the Shippey orchard grown from a bud selected from a productive and desirable parent tree. (Fig. 10.)